

**CONTEMPORARY CHALLENGES AND PROBLEMS IN THE QUALITY OF
TEACHER TRAINING****Zemlyankina Yulianna Iskandarovna****English Language Teacher****Uzbek State University of World Languages****e-mail: uliannazemlankina@gmail.com**

Abstract. Teacher training is a fundamental aspect of the educational system that primarily determines the quality of education at all levels. However, in recent decades, this area has faced a number of serious challenges and obstacles, mainly caused by the need to adapt to rapidly changing societal trends and the demands of the labor market. Without quality teacher training, it is impossible to achieve educational goals and ensure a due level of educational process. In this article, we will take a detailed look at the main modern challenges and problems experienced by the teacher training system, as well as offer possible solutions, the implementation of which, in our opinion, will enhance teacher training and, ultimately, increase the level of education in general.

Key words: education, teacher, teacher training, transformation, globalization, multiculturalism, humanization, empathy.

Following the adoption of the Education Law and the National Personnel Training Program in 1997, continuous education is a core component of the National Personnel Training Model. A completely new, holistic, and scientifically sound system is being created, aligned with the socio-economic transformations in the republic. As noted by the President of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, the basis of any reforms (economic, political, social) lies in the goal of elevating the value of the human being, creating conditions for everyone to receive a good education, a decent job, and to find their place in society. This is the foundation upon which the National Personnel Training Model is built. (<https://president.uz/ru/lists/view/4971>)

In the National Personnel Training Model in the system of continuous education in the Republic of Uzbekistan (February 27, 2020), the following principles of development and implementation are being re-evaluated:

- the prioritization of education – raising the prestige of knowledge, education, and high intelligence.

- democratization of education - expanding the autonomy of educational institutions in choosing methods of teaching and upbringing; accessibility of any type of education for everyone; flexibility of the education system; diversity of educational services.

- humanization of education – orientation of education towards the unique individuality and needs of the person, revealing abilities and creative potential of individuals; ensuring the prioritization of national and universal human values; harmonization of the relationships between the individuals, society, and the environment.

- humanitarianization of education – formation of an aesthetically rich worldview, high spirituality, culture, creative thinking, and social activity.

National orientation of education – the integrity of education with national history, folk traditions and customs, with the aim of preserving and enriching the culture of the peoples of Uzbekistan; recognizing education as the main instrument of national development; respect for the history, culture and values of other peoples

Identification of gifted youth – creating conditions for obtaining fundamental and specialized knowledge at the highest level of education.

According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan «On the Development Strategy of the New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026», special attention is paid to measures to develop national education in order to comply with international standards and create a unified continuous education system and increase the interest of young people in engaging in research activities. (№ UP-60 of 28/01/2022).

Since the key figure in any educational programme is the teacher, who is primarily responsible for the implementation of the educational process at all its stages, the highest priority in education is to improve the quality and effectiveness of teacher training.

Below are several interpretations of the concept of teacher education given in various sources:

- “Teacher education – is a broad and comprehensive, constantly evolving, dynamic and continuous process involving three phases: preparatory, induction and in-service.” (Dunkin, 1987).

- “Teacher education refers to all formal and informal activities designed to prepare a person for or enhance the effectiveness of the teaching profession”. (Good, 1974)

- “Teacher education or teacher education is programs, policies, procedures, and provision designed to equip prospective teachers with the knowledge, attitudes, behaviors, attitudes, techniques, and skills they need to perform their tasks effectively in the classroom, school, and society at large.” (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Teacher_education)

- “Teacher education is the process by which prospective teachers are given the opportunity to develop cognitive, emotional and psychomotor competencies that will enable them to successfully and effectively carry out future teaching activities.” (Ipaye, 1996)

- “Teacher education is the provision of specialized professional training over a period of time to individuals who intend to develop and educate young people to be responsible and productive citizens.” (Oyekan, 2000).

The analysis of these interpretations shows that the main purpose of teacher education is to prepare highly qualified teachers capable of teaching others effectively, in accordance with the requirements of society, education and students of the current era, which seems to be quite a demanding task in teacher training institutions at present. Pedagogy is a universal profession meant to stimulate and develop the mental, physical and emotional abilities of students of different levels of knowledge and performance (Oyekan, 2000). According to Oyekan, educators are expected to be sensitive, imaginative and resourceful as it is their responsibility and duty to promote health, quality of life, peaceful coexistence, environmental management of students as well as educating the latter in the spirit of democracy (Oyekan, 1994).

Any country needs a large number of qualified, well-trained, proficient teachers who should be sufficiently familiar with well-planned educational subjects, professional educational courses, test building principles, classroom evaluation and analysis practices, and the ethics of the teacher's profession. At the same time, the modern teacher, along with fundamental education, should be able to go beyond the framework of pattern thinking, be flexible and dynamic enough not only to react quickly, but to anticipate the changing challenges and demands of the real modern education system, students and society as a whole.

Here arises a question: How to train this kind of specialists? Of course, there is no single or unified approach that can lead to the achievement of the expected results in the field of reformation of the teaching and learning system. Any strategy for change must consider the diverse factors affecting our educational system, the complex interrelation of its parts within it and with the outside environment.

Let us consider four key factors that necessitated the urge to reform the education system:

1) Globalization processes. In the course of erasing geographical boundaries and the expanding interconnection between various countries and cultures, the practice of educational systems and institutions is influenced by and subjected to processes of adoption and adaptation of diverse educational models. Since the modern education system cannot be viewed in isolation from the cultural and political-economic processes involved in most concepts of globalization, the

impact of globalization processes on education is studied as a large-scale phenomenon, not limited to one area or sub-area. The influence of globalization affects the policies and structures of many educational systems, values and ideals, pedagogy, curricula and assessment, as well as the concepts of 'teacher and learner' and 'good life'.

From the perspective of functionalism, the main trends in the globalization of educational systems are new requirements and needs for access to education, both on the part of students and teachers. There is increasing convergence replacing the dichotomous education system in terms of academic levels and qualifications, curricula and assessment, as it is recognized that standardization makes it more possible to move people in education between societies, and that such movement of people can improve education in various ways (creating diversity, increasing specializations and promoting special research centers, increasing global employability, etc.) (Stier, 2004). Accordingly, there is a need to master «interculturality» as one of the main requisites for successful interaction in a multicultural educational community.

2) Digitalization of education. The rapid development of ICT and the forced transition to distance learning during the COVID-19 pandemic have further exposed existing problems in education in many countries, including Uzbekistan. New tasks have emerged for teachers, such as changing their role, creating innovative teaching methods and integrating technology into teaching; development of high-quality electronic learning materials, which primarily requires the formation of teachers' digital competencies.

The growing demand for online courses and programs is also putting pressure on educators in most educational institutions because they lack experience in developing effective online courses, understanding students, and knowledge of how to launch online courses and programs with adequate preparation.

3) Humanization of education. The concept of humanistic pedagogy was first developed by Paulo Freire in the 20th century. Its essence lay in the requirement for educators to strive for social change and to minimize the level of societal oppression (Freire, 2000, p. 129). Humanistic approaches to teaching and learning can be defined as 'the development of the whole person through the acquisition of knowledge, skills, competencies, ethical norms, and thinking habits' (Blessinger, Sengupta & Reshef, 2019).

In the classical and modern educational system of Uzbekistan, spiritual and moral education and national identity have always been given special attention. Uzbek philosophers and scholars have always proclaimed humanitarian ideas of education in harmony with upbringing, emphasizing that the formation and development of a spiritually and morally conscious individual,

who values their homeland, family, and ancestral cultural traditions, contributes to the development of our society and state.

Proceeding from the fact that the concept "spirituality" includes meanings (goals), values (faith), attitude towards others/others and being (lifestyle) (Buch, 2017), the ethno-didactic model of "Usta-Shogird" (master-apprentice), widely used in Uzbekistan, becomes relevant at the angle of the humanistic educational paradigm. As Makhkamova notes, this is a time-tested method whose educational value lies in the transmission, preservation, and multiplication of professionally significant information, social experience, moral and cultural norms and rules of conduct, social traditions, etc. Consequently, the model (method) "Usta-shogird" is acceptable not only for mastering professional competence, but also for the formation of spiritual and moral values as well as ethical standards of behavior of future specialists (Makhkamova, 2024).

A particular problem in the context of the humanization of education today is represented by migratory movements. Many people from crisis and military zones seek help and protection in peaceful countries hoping for asylum, cultural and religious tolerance and improvement in their prospects. However, in the society of host countries, they often face populist right-wing movements, irrational intolerance, ignorance, xenophobia and even aggressive actions, against refugees.

Therefore the humanization of education is also intercultural (multicultural) education, the theoretical and practical task of which is to create equal educational opportunities for students from different racial, ethnic, socio-class and cultural backgrounds, and to provide all students with the knowledge, skills and attitudes necessary for effective functioning in a pluralistic democratic society and harmonious interaction and dialogue between representatives of different groups (Banks & Banks, 1995. p. XI).

In this regard, the development of the empathetic potential of future foreign language specialists, as one of the components of intercultural competence, is of particularly importance. This also includes the socio-emotional competence of future teachers, which is considered part of the relational competence of teachers, i.e., their ability to build positive relationships in the process of pedagogical practice. The main aspects of forming socio-emotional competence in the process of teacher training are: the development of sensitivity in recognizing students' feelings, emotional responsiveness in the group, emotional presence, the ability to manage one's own and others' emotions (for example, putting oneself in another's shoes), as well as recognizing the value of each student and creating an emotionally safe and supportive environment through actions and relationships in a continuous communicative process. This can be achieved through a range of

teaching methods, such as the use of appropriate video, audio, photo and text materials and conducting an analysis or relevant reflection on the materials used.

The importance of affective aspects in teaching practice is also noted by our foreign colleagues (Melo et al., 2018), as much of what a teacher knows and does is connected to their own emotional state and motivation, which directly affects student learning. Therefore, recognizing the importance of the affective aspect in relation to the taught material changes attitudes and increases teaching effectiveness. The affective domain is transformed and integrated into innovation and professional development processes into the specific and didactic content of the taught subject. (Melo, 2018).

The result of the humanization of education in foreign literature is understood as the upbringing of a citizen who is actively committed to democracy, inclusiveness, universal justice, and solidarity (Murga-Menoyo, 2020) in order to achieve greater humanity in social, historical, and transformational contexts (del Carmen Salazar, 2013).

4) Content of the educational programme. The main catalysts for paradigm shifts in education are the transition to a post-industrial society, where knowledge has become the dominant element of the country's economic development, and the university plays a fundamental role in providing it, as well as the dynamic development of technologies that have transformed both access to information and the approach to learning and teaching style (Watson, 2001; Sellen, 2002).

It has become obvious that it is impossible to work effectively in tomorrow's world, learning from outdated competencies. The traditional curriculum, in which more attention is paid to the theoretical part instead of practical work, and teachers are perceived and prepared as transmitters of information from textbooks forced to transfer the content of the program to an inactive group of students, does not meet the requirements of modern society. That is why many studies (Livingston & Shiach, 2009; Mayer, Pecheone & Merino, 2012; Martin & Mulvihill, 2017; Valeeva & Gafurov, 2017) indicate that different countries are making significant efforts to reform their pedagogical education systems and to create new strategies and approaches to meet rapidly changing realities in the education and upbringing of the young generation.

In today's environment of constant dynamic development, acquired knowledge quickly becomes outdated, forcing specialists to acquire new knowledge, skills, and abilities. Therefore, continuous learning and self-education (long-life learning) becomes an integral part of the development of modern specialist competencies. For this reason, modern educators are required to foster students' independent and critical thinking, exploration of certain concepts and patterns,

as well as perseverance, curiosity, and constant aspiration to self-development and personal intellectual growth.

Consequently, in the modern pedagogical education system, along with professional knowledge, more attention should be paid to the so-called «soft» skills and abilities (skills of the 21st century), among which are emotional intelligence, communication skills, intercultural competence, self-awareness, empathy and others that play a crucial role in an individual's personal and professional life. It should also be noted that empathic competence is of paramount significance in inclusive education, which should become an integral part of the educational program of a civilized society, as it is necessary to raise awareness among future teachers about children with special needs.

Summing up, it should be admitted that all transformations of the pedagogical education system should be systematically evaluated in terms of their compliance with the realities of the labor market and the accelerating pace of societal evolutions.

References:

Legislative acts and publications of methodological significance:

Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-60 dated January 28, 2022, On the Strategy for the Development of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 <https://lex.uz/docs/5841077>].

National Model for Personnel Training. System of Continuous Education in the Republic of Uzbekistan February 27, 2020. <https://dereksiz.org/1-nacionalenaya-modele-podgotovki-kadrov-sistema-neprerivnogo.html>. Accessed: November 12, 2023

Regulations on State Educational Standards of January 5, 1998, No. 5. Electronic source: <https://lex.uz/acts/622249>. Accessed: November 12, 2023

1. Banks, J. A. (1995). Multicultural Education and Curriculum Transformation. *The Journal of Negro Education*, 64(4), 390–400. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2967262>
2. del Carmen Salazar, M. (2013). A Humanizing Pedagogy: Reinventing the Principles and Practice of Education as a Journey Toward Liberation. *Review of Research in Education*, 37, 121–148. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/24641959>
3. Dunkin, Michael J. *The International Encyclopedia of Teaching and Teacher Education*. 1st ed, Pergamon Press, 1987.
4. Good, C. V., & Merkel, W. R. (1974). *Dictionary of education* (3rd ed., 4th print). McGraw-Hill.

5. Ipaye, B. (1996). Problems and prospects of teacher education in Nigeria. //P.N. Anikweze C.M and Maiyamaga, A. (eds) *Teacher Education an Imperative for National Development*. – Kaduna: NTI.
6. Oyekan, S.O. (1994). Fundamentals of education. //In W. Osisanwo (Ed.) *Education for Nigeria certificate in education*. – Ondo; Adeyemi college of education textbook development board. – Pp. 1-58.
7. Oyekan, S.O. (2000). *Foundations of teacher education*. – Okitipupa: Ebun-Ola printers Nig. Ltd.
8. Stier J. (2004). Taking a critical stance toward internationalization ideologies in higher education: idealism, instrumentalism and educationalism. // *Globalisation, Societies and Education*. #2. – Pp. 1–28.
9. Freire P. (2000). *Pedagogy of the Oppressed*. – N. Y.: Continuum International Publishing Group. – P. 181.
10. Blessinger, P., Sengupta, E. & Reshef, S. (2019). Humanising higher education via inclusive leadership. – University World News. Retrieved from: <https://www.universityworldnews.com/post.php?story=20190218081816874>
11. Buch H.G. (2017). *Spirituality: Concept Analysis and Model Develop*. // *Holistic Nursing Practice*. Wynnewood. Available: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/6698914>.
12. Livingston, K., and Shiach, L. (2009). Con-constructing a New Model of Teacher Education. In: A. Campbell and S. Groundwater-Smith (Eds.), *Connecting*
13. *Inquiry and Professional Learning in Education: International Perspectives and Practical Solutions* (pp. 83–96). Abingdon: Routledge.
14. Makhkamova
G.T. Problems of spiritual and moral education of students and their solution. //Teaching language and literature. №3, 2024. – P.69-72.
15. Martin, L. E., & Mulvihill, T. M. (2017). Current Issues in Teacher Education: An Interview with Dr. Linda Darling-Hammond. *The Teacher Educator*, 52(2), 75–83. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08878730.2017.1294921>
16. Mayer, D.R., Pecheone, R., and Merino, M. (2012). Rethinking Teacher Education in Australia: The Quality Reforms. In: L. Darling-Hammond and A. Lieberman (Eds.), *Teacher Education around the World. Changing Policies and Practices* (pp. 110–129). London: Routledge.

17. Melo, L., Cañada, F. (2018) Emociones que emergen durante el análisis del conocimiento didáctico del contenido sobre el campo eléctrico.// *Ciência & Educação* (Bauru). Vol. 24, núm. 1. – Pp. 57-70.
18. Murga-Menoyo, M. Ángeles. (2020). The path towards the SDGs: shaping a planetary citizenship through education. *Comillas Journal of International Relations* , (19), 01–11. <https://doi.org/10.14422/cir.i19.y2020.001>.
19. Sellen M. (2002). Information Literacy In The General Education: A New Requirement For The 21st Century. // *Journal of General Education*. Volume: 51. – Pp. 115 –126.
20. Watson, D.M. Pedagogy before Technology: Re-thinking the Relationship between ICT and Teaching. *Education and Information Technologies* **6**, 251–266 (2001). <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1012976702296>

Internet:

<https://president.uz/ru/lists/view/4971>

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Teacher_education